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Optimal selection of wavelet transform parameters for spatio-temporal analysis based on non-stationary NDVI MODIS time series in Mediterranean region

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Abstract:	<p>The multi-resolution analysis based on wavelet transform (WT) has widely proved its effectiveness for the analysis of non-stationary time series (TS) in the remote sensing field. However, there are three essential parameters affecting wavelet-aided data in vegetation dynamics detection. This study proposes a new methodology that serves for the proper selection of the most critical parameters to carry out an optimal analysis for vegetation seasonal and long-term dynamics, specifically adapted to NDVI TS. The specific objectives are: (1) to simulate a TS dataset to understand the best WT parameter performance for trend and seasonal changes detection, and (2) to assess the impact of those WT parameters using NDVI MODIS TS in the Mediterranean area along the period 2001-2019. Different types of trends and WT were considered (i.e., Discrete WT (DWT) and Maximal Overlap DWT (MODWT)) in the simulated dataset. The best WT parameters were calculated based on an iterative algorithm that computes the trend and seasonal components using the optimal level of decomposition for each TS and mother wavelet (MW). Then, the findings obtained from the simulated data were exploited using Earth observation data. In the step, the Theil-Sen's slope (Q) derived for the best MWs was calculated to provide the trend magnitude and direction. The z-score and energy to Shannon entropy ratio (R(S)) were computed to select the most adequate MW based on pixel characterization. On one hand, the simulated results proved the Multi-resolution analysis DWT (MRA-DWT) as the most optimal wavelet type. Level 5 of decomposition was obtained in 99% and 72% of simulated TS according to the trend and seasonal analysis, respectively. Symlet family gave the optimal results in 92% (trend) and 64% (seasonal) of simulated TS. On the other hand, based on R(S), sym12 MW from Symlet family showed the most dominant wavelet for forest, savanna and mosaic land covers, followed by db14 MW from Daubechies family which was dominated in cropland. From more practical adaptation, sym12 was revealed as an effective solution for all the pixels in the Mediterranean area with a relative error lower than 15%. The vegetation change analysis in the Mediterranean area showed a relationship between $[[EQUATION]]$ and precipitation in almost 37% of the area, being Turkey, Greece and North Africa the regions with a high correspondence with precipitation. Around 5% of the study area showed to be possibly affected by land degradation processes.</p>

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Optimal selection of wavelet transform parameters for spatio-temporal analysis based on non-stationary NDVI MODIS time series in Mediterranean region

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Abstract

The multi-resolution analysis based on wavelet transform (WT) has widely proved its effectiveness for the analysis of non-stationary time series (TS) in the remote sensing field. However, there are three essential parameters affecting wavelet-aided data in vegetation dynamics detection. This study proposes a new methodology that serves for the proper selection of the most critical parameters to carry out an optimal analysis for vegetation seasonal and long-term dynamics, specifically adapted to NDVI TS. The specific objectives are: (1) to simulate a TS dataset to understand the best WT parameter performance for trend and seasonal changes detection, and (2) to assess the impact of those WT parameters using NDVI MODIS TS in the Mediterranean area along the period 2001-2019. Different types of trends and WT were considered (i.e., Discrete WT (DWT) and Maximal Overlap DWT (MODWT)) in

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9 the simulated dataset. The best WT parameters were calculated based on an
10 iterative algorithm that computes the trend and seasonal components using
11 the optimal level of decomposition for each TS and mother wavelet (MW).
12 Then, the findings obtained from the simulated data were exploited using
13 Earth observation data. In the step, the Theil-Sens slope (Q) derived for the
14 best MWs was calculated to provide the trend magnitude and direction. The
15 z-score and energy to Shannon entropy ratio ($R(S)$) were computed to select
16 the most adequate MW based on pixel characterization. On one hand, the
17 simulated results proved the **Multi-resolution analysis DWT (MRA-DWT)**
18 as the most optimal wavelet type. Level 5 of decomposition was obtained in
19 99% and 72% of simulated TS according to the trend and seasonal analysis,
20 respectively. Symlet family gave the optimal results in 92% (trend) and 64%
21 (seasonal) of simulated TS. On the other hand, based on $R(S)$, *sym12* MW
22 from Symlet family showed the most dominant wavelet for forest, savanna
23 and mosaic land covers, followed by *db14* MW from Daubechies family which
24 was dominated in cropland. From more practical adaptation, *sym12* was re-
25 vealed as an effective solution for all the pixels in the Mediterranean area
26 with a relative error lower than 15%. The vegetation change analysis in the
27 Mediterranean area showed a relationship between Q_{NDVI} and precipitation
28 in almost 37% of the area, being Turkey, Greece and North Africa the regions
29 with a high correspondence with precipitation. Around 5% of the study area
30 showed to be possibly affected by land degradation processes.

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51 *Keywords:* NDVI series, wavelet transform, wavelet parameters, vegetation
52 dynamics, trend and seasonal changes, Mediterranean region.
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1. Introduction

Vegetation is an important component of terrestrial ecosystems (Piao et al., 2003; Yang et al., 2021). In the last decade, vegetation faced several variations due principally to natural changes (e.g. climatic changes) and anthropogenic changes such as deforestation, overgrazing and urbanization (Qu et al., 2020). These changes have been widely detected and quantified based on multi-temporal Earth observation (EO) satellite data over a global scale (Weiss et al., 2020). The vegetation time series (TS) analysis lies at the cross-road of four U.N. 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)(Agarwal, 2018; Omer and Noguchi, 2020): Life and Land (SDG15) and climate actions (SDG13). The continuous acquisition and temporal resolution are one of the main advantages of medium and coarse-spatial resolution EO data that make it possible to obtain a proper characterization of vegetation phenology over a long period (Zeng et al., 2020). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) TS has been widely used as a quantitative indicator for vegetation change detection and analysis from local and global scales (Silleos et al., 2006; Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; de Jong et al., 2012; Ben Abbes et al., 2018; Rhif et al., 2021). However, NDVI TS are generally non-stationary due to the presence of seasonal and trend variations (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Verbesselt et al., 2010b), being necessary to find adequate vegetation change detection techniques that accurately recognize seasonal, short-term and long-term variations.

Wavelet transform (WT) is an important method for handling non-stationary TS that has been extensively used over the past few decades in several fields such as remote sensing, finance, medicine, etc (Rhif et al., 2019). Indeed, WT

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10 26 is a time-frequency method that proved to be suitable in the remote sensing
11 27 field. It has been investigated in different applications (e.g., multi-scale and
12 28 trend analysis, wavelet-based denoising, wavelet-based feature, etc). The
13 29 importance of using wavelets for vegetation dynamics analysis is justified
14 30 in [Martínez and Gilabert \(2009\)](#) and [Rhif et al. \(2019\)](#). Specifically, WT
15 31 proved its effectiveness in several works ([Percival et al., 2004](#); [Piao et al.,](#)
16 32 [2012](#); [Moreira et al., 2019](#); [Priyadarshi et al., 2020](#)). In particular, the multi-
17 33 resolution discrete WT (MRA-DWT) was investigated to detect and analyse
18 34 vegetation changes ([Sakamoto et al., 2005](#); [Martínez and Gilabert, 2009](#);
19 35 [Campos and Di Bella, 2012](#); [Qiu et al., 2014](#); [Quaye-Ballard et al., 2020](#)).
20 36 This approach has been successfully applied in multiple study areas glob-
21 37 ally distributed (e.g., Spain, Senegal, Argentina, Tunisia, China and Gana)
22 38 using different vegetation indices TS (e.g, Advanced Very High-Resolution
23 39 Radiometer-NDVI, MODIS-NDVI/Enhanced Vegetation Index). The WT
24 40 has demonstrated its ability to better perform trend analysis by using an
25 41 inter-annual component, which is not affected by the noise introduced by the
26 42 seasonal variability of the data. As a result, an important reduction of the
27 43 dispersion and hence of the slope uncertainty was observed as compared to
28 44 other methods ([Martínez and Gilabert, 2009](#)).

29 45 The effectiveness of the WT is largely influenced by the selection of the
30 46 WT type, mother wavelet (MW) and level of decomposition ([Yang et al.,](#)
31 47 [2016](#); [Rhif et al., 2019](#)). In fact, the selection of adequate wavelet param-
32 48 eters are the most indispensable challenge in wavelet analysis. Different
33 49 WT types are described in the literature such as continuous wavelet trans-
34 50 form (CWT), the discrete wavelet transforms (DWT), the maximal Over-

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51 lap Discrete Wavelet Transform (MODWT) and hybrid wavelet (e.g. em-
10 pirical wavelet transform and least-square wavelet transform). Addition-
11 ally, there exist many MW families (e.g., Haar, Daubechies (*dbN*), Coiflets
12 (*coifN*), Symlets (*symN*), BiorSplines (*biorM.N*), ReverseBior (*rbioM.N*),
13 Meyer (*dmey*) and Morlet (*morl*)) (Misiti et al., 2013). In particular, *dmey*,
14 *dbN* and *symN* have been successfully proven to be useful for vegetation TS
15 analysis.
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22 The selection of the best level of decomposition, the MW and the wavelet
23 type has been studied in several fields to improve the performance of the
24 related methods. The level of decomposition with the dominant frequency
25 defined by a purely periodic signal was introduced by Meyers et al. (1993)
26 and Abry (1997) and it was considered as the most appropriate level of de-
27 composition for vegetation TS trend analysis (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009).
28 Additionally, Jaffery et al. (2012) measured the entropy of the signal at each
29 node to select the best level for speech denoising. The optimal level of decom-
30 position was considered when the entropy of the approximation coefficient
31 was less than the entropy of the different detail coefficients. Lei et al. (2013)
32 exploited the sparseness of the signal to determine the appropriate level and
33 Bakhshi et al. (2013) calculated the best level for trend estimation for elec-
34 trocardiography using the cross-correlation between the original signal and
35 DWT derived detail components based on 53 MW. Moreover, Yang et al.
36 (2016) discussed the selection of the optimal level for hydrological TS mod-
37 elling introducing a backpropagation neural network. Recently, Rahim et al.
38 (2020) considered the wavelet energy as the features extraction to determine
39 the optimum level of decomposition that contributes to the failure of the
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76 suspension system.

77 The MW selection is considered a key factor that may affect the analysis
78 of intra- and inter- annual changes (Gao and Yan, 2010; Rhif et al., 2021). In
79 the literature, the majority of works are based on quantitative approaches.
80 For example, Singh and Tiwari (2006) proposed a procedure for the selection
81 of MW based on the cross-correlation between electrocardiography signal and
82 selected wavelet filter (low pass). They concluded that the *db8* was the most
83 appropriate for the electrocardiography signal. However, according to Sang
84 et al. (2009), the selection of MW is based first on mathematical proper-
85 ties of wavelet family (e.g. regularity, the trade-off between time and scale
86 resolutions and linear phase wavelet) and entropy-based wavelet denoising
87 method. Additionally, the maximum relative wavelet energy (Gawali et al.,
88 2015), minimum relative wavelet entropy (Hafiz et al., 2019) and energy to
89 entropy ratio (Hafiz et al., 2019; Rhif et al., 2021) were investigated for the
90 best MW selection in different fields such as fault detection, identification of
91 power quality, vegetation trend analysis, etc.

92 The selection of the wavelet type is one of the most relevant parameters
93 that affect the coefficients obtained from the WT. Principally, in the remote
94 sensing field, the DWT and MODWT were investigated for multi-temporal
95 vegetation analysis (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Rhif et al., 2019). Re-
96 cently, several studies have paid attention to the selection of WT types in
97 different fields (e.g. finance and medicine). For example, the autocorrela-
98 tion method was exploited to select the best WT type (DWT or MODWT)
99 (Dghais et al., 2013; Ali and Sharif, 2018). Raghu et al. (2020) compared
100 DWT and MODWT based on entropies ratio (i.e., sigmoid, Shannon, wavelet,

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101 Renyi, Tsallis and Steins unbiased risk estimator entropies) in each sub-band.

102 Although there has been active research in using WT for non-stationary
103 TS analysis, there still remains challenges to address the most appropriate
104 wavelet parameters (i.e., type, level of decomposition, and MW). Currently,
105 there is not consensus in literature regarding which WT is better. In fact,
106 Rhif et al. (2021) demonstrated that important contrast Sents slopes values
107 and significant percentage pixels were obtained when different MWs were
108 implemented in long-term vegetation change analysis. Hence, a direct impact
109 in vegetation changes interpretation would be expected.

110 Focusing on the above problem, the main objective of this paper is to
111 advance in this research by proposing a new methodology that selects the
112 three most relevant WT parameters (i.e. the best level of decomposition,
113 the MW and the wavelet type) in order to provide an optimal analysis of
114 vegetation long-term and seasonal changes specifically adapted to the TS
115 type. The specific objectives of this study are:

- 116 1. Examine the use of simulated NDVI TS dataset for the proper selection
117 of the best WT parameters (i.e. level of decomposition, WT type and
118 MW family.
119
- 120 2. Obtain the main conclusions from simulated scenarios analysis and
121 transfer them to real data in order to explore the impact of best MW
122 selection for vegetation long-term and seasonal changes assessment.
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- 124 3. Explore the choice of WT parameters based on different land cover
125 types and climatic data.

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10 126 To this end, a WT theoretical background is first introduced followed by
11 127 the study area and the used data. Then, the description of the proposed
12 128 methodology for WT parameter selection is presented; finally, the benefits
13 129 and limits of the proposed approach are discussed.
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18 130 **2. Theoretical background**

19 131 *2.1. The wavelet Transform*

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21 132 WT is a time-frequency method for non-stationary TS analysis that de-
22 133 composes the signal into different timescales. It is based on two parameters
23 134 namely MW (ψ) and scale function. This later accounts for the lowest fre-
24 135 quencies of the TS (smoother variations), while, the MW introduces the
25 136 highest frequencies (detailed part) of the TS by scale (Crowley, 2005). In
26 137 fact, the WT is defined as a set of fundamental functions $\psi_{s,u}(t)$ that can
27 138 be generated by translating and scaling the so-called MW, $\psi(t)$, as follow
28 139 (Daubechies, 1992):

$$29 \psi_{s,u}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \psi\left(\frac{t-u}{s}\right) \quad (1)$$

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33 140 where s and u determine the scale parameters and the location of the MW,
34 141 respectively. A detailed description can be found in (Daubechies, 1992).
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38 142 *2.2. Wavelet transform types*

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41 143 **Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT):** The DWT decomposes the
42 144 signal into a mutually orthogonal set of a MW (Daubechies, 1992) scaled
43 145 and translated. The MW (ψ) is scaled as $s = 2^j$ and translated by $u = k2^j$,
44 146 where j runs from 0 to J . J is the total number of scales, k is the index
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9 location, which runs from 1 to $2^{-j}N$ and N is the number of observations.
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11 DWT is expressed as follow:
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$$\psi_{j,k}(t) = 2^{-j/2}\psi(2^{-j}t - k) \quad (2)$$

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17 As a hierarchical presentation of DWT, the multiresolution analysis (MRA-
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19 DWT) is defined. This method decomposes the original TS into j levels using
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21 low-pass (LP) and high-pass (HP) filters to translate and convolve succes-
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23 sively the MW. Basically, two components are preserved by these filters, the
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25 detail (D) and approximation (A).
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27 **Maximal Overlap Discrete Wavelet Transform (MODWT):** The
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29 MODWT is an improved representation of DWT proposed by [Percival and](#)
30
31 [Walden \(2000\)](#). It is a linear filtering operation that converts a sequence
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33 into coefficients associated with variations through a range of scales ([Cor-](#)
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35 [nish et al., 2006](#)). The MODWT allows for a more flexible time-frequency
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37 representation of a signal using variable-length windows. Similar to DWT,
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39 the MRA based on MODWT decomposes the TS into A and D components.
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41 However, the MRA-MODWT provides more additional features compared to
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43 MRA-DWT.
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163 *2.3. Mother wavelet properties*

164 The selection of the optimal MW is the primary task in all WT analy-
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166 ses, unlike other transformation techniques whose basis functions were fixed.
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168 The results of TS are very sensitive to the MW used. The MW are dis-
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170 tinctive by their properties. First, the orthogonal Daubechies (dbN) MW
family with compact support is considered where $N(N = 1..45)$ refers to
the MW order. The $db1$ is known as Haar wavelet and it is the simplest

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10 and oldest one. The main properties for dbN are asymmetry, orthogonality
11 with compact support and regularity. The dbN MWs are characterized by a
12 maximal number of vanishing moments for some given support (Daubechies,
13 1992; Misiti et al., 2013). Similarly, to dbN , Symlet ($symN$) MWs exhibit
14 173 174 the same properties of dbN except for the symmetry. Contrarily, Coiflets
15 175 ($CoifN$) family has unusual properties compared to dbN and $symN$. It is
16 176 the most compactly supported MWs with the highest number of vanishing
17 177 moments. Also, the wavelets associated with $coifN$ (N varies for 1 to 5)
18 178 have $2N$ zero moments, but also the scaling function has $(2N - 1)$ zero mo-
19 179 ments. Second, the biorthogonal MWs with compact support presents an
20 180 extension of orthogonal wavelets. The biorthogonal wavelets ($bior\ 1.3$, $bior$
21 181 1.5 , $bior\ 2.2$, $bior\ 2.4$, $bior\ 2.6$, $bior\ 2.8$, $bior\ 3.1$, $bior\ 3.3$, $bior\ 3.5$, $bior$
22 182 3.7 , $bior\ 3.9$, $bior\ 4.4$, $bior\ 5.5$, $bior\ 6.8$) are not based on vanishing moment
23 183 and have symmetric structure. The reverse biorthogonal wavelets ($rbio1.1$,
24 184 $rbio1.3$, $rbio1.5$, $rbio2.2$, $rbio2.4$, $rbio2.6$, $rbio2.8$, $rbio3.1$, $rbio3.3$, $rbio3.5$,
25 185 $rbio3.7$, $rbio3.9$, $rbio4.4$, $rbio5.5$, $rbio6.8$) are based on a coupled biorthog-
26 186 onal wavelet. For this reason, both MW families have the same properties.
27 187 Finally, the approximation of the Meyer wavelet ($dmey$) is an orthogonal MW
28 188 with non-compact support. It requires the use of infinite impulse response
29 189 filters and enables fast decomposition.

30 3. Material

31 3.1. Study area

32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65
192 The study area belongs to the Mediterranean region covered by 39 coun-
193 tries from Europe, Asia and North Africa (Fig.1). The selected area is situ-

Figure 1: The study area belongs to the Mediterranean region located approximately between 10°W 41°E and 27°N 50°N.

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10 194 ated approximately between 10°W 41°E and 27°N 50°N. Such a wide region
11 195 is expected to include important distinctions in vegetation due to climatic
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13 196 and topographical variations and diverse vegetation populations, soil types
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15 197 and land uses. The Mediterranean region is one of the world's top biodiver-
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17 198 sity hotspots. It is specified by a huge area of natural, nearly wild and forest
18
19 199 that has been untouched by human. Additionally, the Mediterranean region
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21 200 is specified with more than 25000 species of plants ([Cuttelod et al., 2009](#))
22
23 201 which make it an interesting and representative area.

24
25 202 Most areas of the Mediterranean region are drylands. Spatially, the north
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27 203 part of Africa and West Asia are dominated by hyper-arid and semi-arid
28
29 204 drylands, while Turkey, Spain and the coastal regions of Morocco and Algeria
30
31 205 are characterized by semi-arid drylands. This specificity of climate has a
32
33 206 profound effect on the region's vegetation and wildlife.

35 207 *3.2. Data description*

36 37 208 *3.2.1. Simulated NDVI data*

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39 209 Three types of NDVI TS were simulated (*SNDVI*) by extracting the key
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41 210 characteristics of MOD13A2 data: *SNDVI* trend (without seasonal varia-
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43 211 tion), *SNDVI* seasonal (without trend) and *SNDVI* TS (including seasonal
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45 212 variation and trend). The simulated data were based on different natural
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47 213 biomes (forest and grassland), accounting for the most different phenology
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49 214 in the study area (forest and grassland present 8.13% and 11.29% in the
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51 215 Mediterranean area).

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53 216 In order to provide a NDVI TS data set that mimic the full range of possi-
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55 217 ble real vegetation TS, the mean, trend, inter-annual variability, seasonality
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57 218 and short-term variability were estimated for all observed NDVI in a simple

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219 step-wise approach:

- 220 1. The first step consisted on creating a synthetic TS without trend. The
221 mean of each NDVI TS was calculated and the simulated seasonal
222 was created using an asymmetric Gaussian function for each season
223 whose amplitude are listed in Table 1. This Gaussian-type function has
224 been shown to perform satisfactorily when used to extract seasonality
225 by fitting the function to TS (Jonsson and Eklundh, 2002; Verbesselt
226 et al., 2010a). The amplitude was set between 0.1 and 0.5, which
227 corresponded to the real seasonal amplitude found in grassland and
228 forest biomes.
- 229 2. A linear trend with an abrupt change taking place at the beginning of
230 the TS was introduced. Different disturbances of a certain magnitude
231 were considered in the simulated TS. The accuracy of the approach
232 for estimating the number, timing, and magnitude of sudden changes
233 was evaluated. A simple disturbance was created by combining a step
234 function of known amplitude (Table 1) and a linear recovery phase
235 (Verbesselt et al., 2010a).
- 236 3. The noise was generated using a normal distribution $N(\mu = 0, \sigma = x)$
237 where x values ranged between 0.01 and 0.07 to approximate the real
238 grass and forest canopies behaviour (Verbesselt et al., 2010a). The
239 vegetation index particular noise was created by randomly substituting
240 white noise with noise with a value of 0.1, which represents cloud con-
241 tamination that frequently remains after atmospheric correction and
242 cloud masking operations.

243 All the combinations of the selected parameters (i.e. amplitude, noise

Table 1: Values of the different parameters for simulated NDVI TS.

Parameters	Values	Time step
Amplitude	[0.1 - 0.5]	0.1
Noise	[0.01 - 0.07]	0.01
Magnitude	[-0.3 - 0.1]	0.1
Slope	0.005, 0.010, 0.020	-
Number of years	19	-
Frequency (observation/year)	23	-

and magnitude of change) (Table 1) were used to create the different TS: *SNDVI*, *SNDVI trend* and *SNDVI seasonal*.

An example of some simulated TS *SNDVI*, trend (*tSNDVI*) and seasonal (*sSNDVI*) is illustrated in Fig.2. *SNDVI1* and *SNDVI2* were characterized by a monotonic negative and positive trend, respectively, whereas the *SNDVI3* and *SNDVI4* included a negative and positive trend with a sudden NDVI drop in 2011. Two abrupt changes in NDVI TS were considered for *SNDVI5*, one in 2008 and another one in 2016. Site *SNDVI6* was also considered with a negative trend from 2001-2010, but followed by a positive trend between 2010-2016 and 2016-2019. *SNDVI7* was characterized by two negative NDVI trend periods (i.e. 2001-2007, 2014-2017) with a positive trend for the periods 2007-2014 and 2017-2019, and *SNDVI8* with a general positive trend behaviour and few negative trends in 2004, 2006 and 2012.

Figure 2: Examples of simulated NDVI TS.

3.2.2. *EO-based NDVI dataset*

In this study, the 16-day composite NDVI TS was considered from the MOD13A2 (v006) data product (Didan, 2015) at 1 km along the period 2001-2019. The dataset was freely available from the website of Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center or LP DAAC (<https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/>) which is maintained by U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). Tiles from h17v04, h17v06 until h21v4, h21v06 were downloaded to cover the study area. For every date, all the tiles were mosaicked to obtain a single image and reprojected from Integerized Sinusoidal into a geographic coordinate system (longitude/latitude). Finally, a pre-processing step was required due to cloud-contaminated or unreliable pixels presented in the TS (Jia et al., 2011). The pixel reliability layer derived from the MOD13A2 was used to discard

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10 269 those pixels with low and unsatisfactory quality. Pixels with more than 50%
11 270 of reliable values (i.e., rank 0 or pixels unaffected by atmospheric obstruc-
12 271 tions) were only considered. Those pixels were filtered and reconstructed
13 272 using the locally estimated scatter plot smoothing method (LOESS). This
14 273 method has proved its effectiveness in noise reduction and gap filling EO-
15 274 based data (Moreno et al., 2014) and has given better performance compared
16 275 to Double Logistic, smoothing spline, Interpolation for Data Reconstruction,
17 276 and adaptive Savitzky-Golay. Indeed, the LOESS method interpolates the
18 277 missing data and removes most of the aberrant values from the original TS.

27 3.2.3. MODIS Land cover dataset

29 The 500 m annual MODIS land cover product (MCD12Q1 v006) was also
30 280 considered for the studied period. Two images were downloaded from the LP
31 281 DAAC source for 2001 and 2019. Similar to MODIS NDVI pre-processing
32 282 step, the MCD12Q1 images were mosaicked, reprojected into geographic co-
33 283 ordinates and resized to 1-km spatial resolution. Different classification meth-
34 284 ods are available in this dataset (e.g. International Geosphere-Biosphere
35 285 Programme (IGBP) classification, Leaf Area Index (LAI) classification, etc).
36 286 In this paper, the 17-class IGBP global vegetation classification scheme was
37 287 selected instead of other available classifications. In fact, IGBP classifica-
38 288 tion is related to physical characteristics of the surface, especially vegetation
39 289 (Friedl et al., 2002). To simplify the analysis, a more general land cover was
40 290 proposed by combining related land cover types from IGPB. Therefore, a
41 291 generalized classification of 9 land cover classes was obtained by aggregat-
42 292 ing similar land cover classes from the 17-class IGBP resulting in: bare area
43 293 (37%), cropland (23%), savanna (13%), grassland (11%), forest (8%), shrub-

Figure 3: Land cover classification derived from MCD12Q1 data in 2019. Land cover change presents pixels where the land cover change from 2001 and 2019.

land (4%), mosaic (2%), urban areas (2%) and wetlands (0.3%). Although the number of classes was reduced as a result of this simplification, the basic geographical patterns were preserved. As presented in Fig.3, 10.3% of pixels faced change between 2001 and 2019 (i.e. pixels presented in black).

3.2.4. Precipitation dataset

The 12-month Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) (McKee et al., 1993; Ji and Peters, 2003) data over the period 2001-2019 was investigated to enhance the identification and understanding of vegetation changes. This

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302 index is based on the probability of precipitation and it quantifies precipita-
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303 tion anomalies by transforming observed precipitation into a normal distribu-
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304 tion for a specific time period ([World Meteorological Organization \(WMO\),](#)
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305 [2012](#)). The SPI approach has several advantages including its simplicity and
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306 temporal flexibility, which allow its application to identify areas affected by
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307 drought and wet events on all timescales. The 12-month SPI was computed
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308 using the monthly Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission Multi-Satellite Pre-
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309 cipitation Analysis Rainfall Estimate Product 3B43 Version 7 (V7) ([Kum-](#)
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310 [merow et al., 2000; Liu et al., 2017](#)) (<http://trmm.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). This
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311 product merges satellite rainfall estimates with gauge data into gridded es-
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312 timates on a monthly temporal resolution and a 0.25°by 0.25°spatial resolu-
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313 tion global band extending from 50°S to 50°N latitude. Several studies have
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314 demonstrated the 3B43 monthly data a good performance and an acceptable
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315 accuracy in many research fields ([Liu et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020](#)).

316 The 12-month SPI dataset for 2001-2019 was spatially interpolated to 1-
317 km spatial resolution by a simple nearest neighbour resampling method since
318 it is computationally efficient and preserves the input image pixel values. For
319 any given region, positive SPI ($> +1$) values are indicated increasingly severe
320 excess rainfall, while negative values (< -1) are referred to as increasingly
321 rainfall deficits (i.e. meteorological droughts).

322 *3.2.5. Validation datasets*

323 Three datasets are considered for evaluating the proposed methodology
324 along the period 2001-2019:

- 325 • The 16-day composite NDVI TS was considered from the MOD13Q1
326 (v006) data product at 250m.

- 327 • The 16-day composite NDVI TS derived from the MOD13A1 (v006)
328 data product at 500m.
- 329 • The monthly composite NDVI TS obtained from the MOD13A3 (v006)
330 data product at 1km.

331 All the datasets were freely available from the website of Land Processes
332 Distributed Active Archive Center or LP DAAC ([https://lpdaac.usgs.](https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/)
333 [gov/](https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/)) which is maintained by USGS.

334 4. Experimental procedure

335 4.1. Best wavelet parameters selection based on simulated data

336 The selection of the best wavelet parameters was divided into three steps
337 as presented in Fig.4, the selection of the best level of decomposition, the
338 choice of the optimal MW, and finally the selection of the WT type. The
339 suggested algorithm searched for better solutions by iterating the method
340 that solved the three problems sequentially.

341 The inputs of the proposed algorithm were $SNDVI$, simulated trend
342 ($tSNDVI$) and simulated seasonal ($sSNDVI$) introduced in section 3.2.1.
343 Then, three variables (i, j, k) were initialized to 1, where $i = \{1, \dots, \text{number of}$
344 $SNDVI\}$, $j = \{1, \dots, \text{number of MWs}\}$ and $k = \{1, \dots, \text{number of types}\}$. The
345 different steps are described as follow:

346 *Step 1: Best level decomposition.* First, the maximum number of levels
347 (L) in which each $SNDVI(i)$ can be decomposed using every $MW_{j,k}$ was
348 obtained as (Yang et al., 2016):

$$L = \text{Log}_2(\text{length}(SNDVI(i))) \quad (3)$$

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Figure 4: A proposed methodology based on simulated data for optimum wavelet bases selection.

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349 The best level depends on the MW since the temporal scale and the MW
10 frequency require to be linked (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009). The dominant
11 MW frequency is commonly characterized by establishing a simple periodic
12 signal of the period (Meyers et al., 1993; Abry, 1997):
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$$p = a \frac{\Delta t}{v_c} \quad (4)$$

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353 where a is the timescale, v_c is the centre frequency of the selected discrete
354 wavelet in Hz, and Δt is the sampling period of the TS. First, the level
355 corresponding to a semi-period ($p/2$) closer to 365 days (L_A) was selected for
356 every $MW_{j,k}$ since this is the minimum time scale require for trend analysis
357 (i.e. inter-annual vegetation dynamic analysis).

358 Second, the best level was computed using the cross-correlation between
359 the $SNDVI(i)$ and each detailed wavelet coefficients (WT_{DL}):

$$corr(SNDVI_i) = \frac{[WT_{DL} - \mu_{WT_{DL}}]^T [SNDVI(i) - \mu_{SNDVI(i)}]}{\sigma_{WT_{DL}} \sigma_{SNDVI(i)}} \quad (5)$$

360 where $(\mu_{WT_{DL}}, \sigma_{WT_{DL}})$ and $(\mu_{SNDVI(i)}, \sigma_{SNDVI(i)})$ account for the mean and
361 standard deviation of the $SNDVI(i)$ and detailed component at scale l re-
362 spectively. The obtained correlation value was related to variations on the
363 scale $2^l (l = 1 \dots L)$. Thus, the highest correlation value would inform about
364 the level (L_D) which accounts for a major contribution due to seasonal vari-
365 ability. Considering the decomposition until this level assured the minimum
366 losses of information due to vegetation phenology and seasonal dynamics.

367 As presented in Fig.4, the $SNDVI$ were decomposed using L level (eq. 3)
368 for all MW. Then, L_A (eq. 4) and L_D (eq. 5) were calculated in parallel to
369 verify the best level for trend and seasonal analysis. Therefore, we consider
370 the best level ($L_A = L_D + 1$). Based on previous findings derived from

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371 [Martínez and Gilabert \(2009\)](#) study, only those $MW_{j,k}$ which L_A agrees with
372 one level more than the L_D will be considered for our study ($L_A = L_D + 1$).
373 Otherwise, the $MW_{j,k}$ will be dismissed and will not be considered for the
374 next step using $SNDVI(i)$ and $Type_k$.

375 *Step 2: Optimal MW.* After selecting the best level for each $SNDVI(i)$ and
376 $MW_{j,k}$, the next part was to select the optimal MW. First, each $SNDVI(i)$
377 was decomposed again using the best level and each $MW_{j,k}$ from the $Type_k$.
378 As a result, both trend ($tSNDVI(i,j,k)$) and seasonal ($sSNDVI(i,j,k)$) com-
379 ponents were derived. The trend component was associated with the last
380 approximation component ($A_{bestLevel}$) of the $Type_k$ whereas the seasonal TS
381 was calculated as the sum of different detailed components from level 2 as
382 $V = D_2 + D_3 + \dots + D_{bestLevel}$. Then, trend ($tSNDVI(i,j,k)$) and simulated
383 trend ($tSNDVI(i)$) were compared. Similarly, a comparison between the
384 seasonal component ($sSNDVI(i,j,k)$) and simulated seasonal ($sSNDVI(i)$)
385 was performed. The root means square error (RMSE), Minkowski distance
386 (D_{mink}) and Pearson correlation (r) coefficient ([Martínez and Gilabert, 2009](#);
387 [Lhermitte et al., 2011](#); [Jamali et al., 2015](#); [Forkel et al., 2013](#); [Verbesselt et al.,](#)
388 [2010a](#); [Ali and Sharif, 2018](#)) were computed as follow:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x(i) - y(i))^2} \quad (6)$$

$$D_{mink} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N |(x(i) - y(i))|^2 \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x(i) - \bar{x}(i))(y(i) - \bar{y}(i))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x(i) - \bar{x}(i))^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (y(i) - \bar{y}(i))^2}} \quad (8)$$

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391 where N is the size of TS analysed for the seasonal and trend components,
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392 $x(i)$ is the obtained season and trend TS from the $Type_k$ and $y(i)$ regards
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13 393 to the simulated ones. $\bar{x}(i)$ and $\bar{y}(i)$ represent the sample mean of $x(i)$ and
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15 394 $y(i)$ respectively. This step was repeated for all $MW_{j,k}$ for the same TS. The
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17 395 $MW_{j,k}$, which showed the lowest RMSE, D_{min} and highest r for both trend
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19 396 and seasonal components, was considered as the best MW for each $SNDVI$.
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21 397 Both step 1 and 2 were repeated for all simulated TS. Therefore, the optimal
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23 398 MW for $Type_k$ and best level obtained for each $SNDVI(i)$ were considered.

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25 399 *Step 3: Best type selection.* For the selection of the best type, the two
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27 400 previous steps were reproduced. The parameters which showed the lowest
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29 401 RMSE, D_{min} and the greatest r were considered for optimal type, MW and
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402 scale for $SNDVI(i)$.

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32 403 In this paper, two WT types (i.e. DWT and MODWT) were used. Ad-
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34 404 ditionally, MWs with filters were selected since MRA is required for seasonal
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36 405 and trend components analysis. Within this category, we can find the orthog-
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38 406 onal and biorthogonal MWs distribution. Thus, 119 MWs (i.e. Haar ($db1$),
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40 407 Daubechies ($db2-45$), Symlet ($sym2-45$), Coiflets ($coif1-5$), Meyer ($dmey$),
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42 408 Biorthogonal ($bior$) and Reverse Biorthogonal ($rbio$)) were considered using
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44 409 MRA-DWT, whereas only 89 MWs (i.e. $db1$, $db2-45$, $sym2-45$, $coif1-5$ and
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46 410 $dmey$) were used with MRA-MODWT. These MWs were selected based on
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48 411 their mathematical properties detailed in section 2.3.

50 412 4.2. Application using EO-based NDVI data

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52 413 This section explains the experimental procedure to better adapt the
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54 414 main findings of section 4.1 to EO-based NDVI TS for vegetation change
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56 415 detection. To deal with this objective, the last approximation component

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416 (i.e. trend component) $A_{bestLevel}$ derived from the best type was considered
417 to examine the inter-annual vegetation changes.

418 The methodology for studying vegetation dynamics in the Mediterranean
419 area using the optimal wavelet parameters was divided into two steps. In the
420 first step, the impact of MW selection for vegetation change analysis was
421 assessed. The NDVI TS were decomposed using the best type, best level
422 and different MWs (i.e. best and worst MWs) obtained from section 4.1.
423 In addition, The worst MWs were used to show the impact of MW selec-
424 tion using EO-based data. Then, trend ($A_{bestLevel}$ component was derived to
425 extract the magnitude and direction of the trend component from the combi-
426 nation of non-parametric Mann-Kendall and Theil-Sens slope (Q) methods.
427 Theil-Sens slope method has been widely used and recommended for the as-
428 sessment of the NDVI TS trend (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Schucknecht
429 et al., 2013; Rhif et al., 2021). A detailed description of Q is available in Sen
430 (1968).

431 The Q image was exploited to compare the vegetation change using
432 best and worst MWs. Dependencies between two Q images using different
433 MW were visually identified. Additionally, the root mean square difference
434 (RMSD) (eq.6), mean bias difference (MBD) and r (eq.8) were calculated.
435 The MBD is computed as:

$$MBD = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x(i) - y(i)| \quad (9)$$

436 where $x(i)$ and $y(i)$ present the Q of two different MWs and N is the length of
437 significant pixels. Additionally, the correlation between MWs was analysed
438 based on land cover type. MWs with a low RMSE value were considered as

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439 the best MW for every pixel.

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11 In a second step, the selection of the most adequate MW based on the
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13 441 pixel was analysed. For this purpose, the Q images derived from different
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15 442 MWs were transformed to z -score values. This transformation describes how
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17 443 much far and in which direction a Q_i value for a specific MW deviates from
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19 444 the Q distribution's mean considering all the Q images. For each Q image,
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21 445 the z -score was calculated by subtracting the mean ($\mu_{i,j}$) value of each ij
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23 446 pixel when considering the four trends values (one for each wavelet); this
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25 447 difference was then divided by the standard deviation ($\sigma_{i,j}$) for the mean of
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27 448 each pixel. It is measured in standard deviation units allowing to compare
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29 449 the four images and was calculated as:

$$30 \quad z\text{-score}_{ij}^{MW} = \frac{Q_{ij}^{MW} - \mu_{i,j}}{\sigma_{i,j}} \quad (10)$$

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33 450 where Q_{ij}^{MW} presents the Theil-Sens slope of the selected MW and pixel ij .

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35 In a third step, the maximum energy to Shannon entropy ratio $R(S)$
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37 451 was investigated (Rhif et al., 2021) to help in the optimal MW selection for
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39 452 each pixel. This ratio computes the dominant wavelet coefficients as the
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41 453 maximum energy level. Then, these coefficients were used to calculate the
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43 454 Shannon entropy for each MW. The $R(S)$ was determined (Rodrigues et al.,
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45 455 2016; Rhif et al., 2021):
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$$47 \quad R(S) = \frac{Energy(S)}{Entropy} \quad (11)$$

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50 457 where $Energy(S) = \sum_{i=1}^n |Wt_D NDVI(i)|^2$ and $Entropy = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2(p_i)$.
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52 458 n is the number of wavelet coefficients at each scale, Wt_D are the detailed
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54 459 wavelet coefficients and the energy probability distribution of the wavelet
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56 460 coefficient (p_i) defined as: $p_i = \frac{|Wt(S,i)|^2}{Energy(S)}$. The MW with the highest $R(S)$
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10 461 was considered as the optimal MW for each NDVI(i) pixel in the detection of
11 462 trend changes. The rationale behind the use of the highest value of $R(S)$ will
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13 463 yield high magnitudes of wavelet coefficients. Meanwhile, the corresponding
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15 464 energy will be large, and the energy concentration will be high (Yang and
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17 465 Wang, 2015). The highest $R(S)$ would assure the wavelet with maximum
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19 466 information is considered to better infer vegetation changes in different land
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21 467 covers.

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23 468 Finally, the best obtained parameters were used for vegetation change
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25 469 analysis. In fact, the Q_{NDVI} was first analysed to understand the land cover
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27 470 change. Additionally, the detail component ($D_{bestLevel-1}$) was taken into ac-
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29 471 count to explore the intra-annual changes or seasonal variability. More specif-
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31 472 ically, the timing of the maximum NDVI in the component $D_{bestLevel-1}(t_{max})$
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33 473 was computed in order to infer important features of seasonal vegetation dy-
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35 474 namics (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009). SPI data was also used to validate our
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37 475 approach and gain a better knowledge of the prominent vegetation dynamic
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39 476 processes observed in the study area (e.g. noticeable increase or decrease of
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41 477 vegetation). Cross-correlation between the Q_{NDVI} and SPI Theil-Sens slope
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43 478 (Q_{SPI}) was derived to analyse the relationship between meteorological data
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45 479 and vegetation changes. In this analysis, we considered that the average
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47 480 annual precipitation plays an important role in the inter-annual response of
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49 481 vegetation to episodes where the regime of precipitation has been altered
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51 482 (Chamailé-Jammes and Fritz, 2009).
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483 5. Results and discussion

484 5.1. Simulated data

485 All the simulated TS were decomposed until level 8 (i.e. $\log_2(436)$) (eq.3).
486 Corresponding periods and semi-periods for the particular TS SNDVI1 using
487 different MWs and both MRA-DWT and MRA-MODWT are highlighted
488 in Table 2. It is clear that level 5 corresponded to a pseudo-period ($p/2$)
489 around 385. Similar results were obtained for different SNDVI TS, MW and
490 MRA-MODWT type. The MRA-DWT approach provided inter-annual levels
491 around 5 except for some MWs (i.e. *db1*, *bior2.2*, *bior2.4*, *bior2.6*, *bior2.8*,
492 *bior3.1*, *bior3.3*, *bior3.5*, *bior3.7*, *bior3.9*, *rbio1.1*, *rbio1.3* and *rbio3.1*) where
493 the $L_A = 6$.

494 Fig.5 illustrates the cross-correlation coefficients between SNDVI1 and
495 each detailed wavelet coefficients using different MW types. The decompo-
496 sition level 4 maximized the correlation coefficients for all the simulated TS.
497 The same result was obtained for the different combinations of parameters.
498 The $L_D = 4$ was exhibited as the most appropriate for the analysis of the
499 intra-annual vegetation variation for all MWs, SNDVI and WT type. In
500 fact, $L_D = 4$ may be related to semi-annual variations typical of seasonal
501 cycle (because its semi-period is between 160-203 days). Thus, the next level
502 $L_A = 5$ was exhibited as the best level for the inter-annual vegetation varia-
503 tions for MRA-DWT as well as MRA-MODWT. However, 13 MW were not
504 considered in the rest of the study specifically with MRA-DWT type which
505 have the $L_D + 1 \neq L_A$ (i.e. MW with $L_A = 6$).

506 In this step, the period and correlation coefficients calculated in Eq.4 and
507 Eq.5 were used to select the best level of decomposition for seasonal and trend

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Table 2: Pseudo-period ($p/2$) for SNDVI1 using different MW (*db14*, *sym12*, *sym21*, *coif5*, *dmey*, *bior1.5* and *rbio6.8*), (*db2*, *db45*, *sym3*, *coif2*, *dmey*) for MRA-DWT and MRA-MODWT respectively.

WT Type	MW	Level							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
		Scale							
		2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256
MRA-DWT	<i>Db14</i>	24	48	96	192	384	768	1536	3072
	<i>sym12</i>	23	46	92	184	368	736	1472	2944
	<i>sym21</i>	23	46	94	187	375	750	1499	2999
	<i>coif5</i>	23	46	93	186	371	742	1485	2970
	<i>dmey</i>	24	48	96	192	384	768	1536	3072
	<i>bior1.5</i>	21	41	82	165	329	658	1316	2632
	<i>rbio6.8</i>	25	49	99	198	396	791	1582	3164
MRA-MODWT	<i>Db2</i>	24	48	96	192	384	768	1536	3072
	<i>db45</i>	25	51	102	203	407	814	1627	3255
	<i>sym3</i>	20	40	80	160	320	640	1280	2560
	<i>Coif2</i>	22	44	88	176	352	704	1408	2816
	<i>dmey</i>	24	48	96	193	386	772	1544	3087

508 analysis. Level 5 seemed to be the most appropriate since it accounts for
509 inter- and intra-annual variation (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009). Therefore,
510 the derived MRA approximation components A_5 ensured the slope of long-

Figure 5: Comparison of the normalized correlation coefficient for various wavelet filters for SNDVI1

511 term changes could be assessed over the considered period (i.e. 2001-2019).
 512 These results were in accordance with those obtained in previous studies
 513 using 1-km NDVI dataset (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Vicente-Serrano
 514 et al., 2020).

515 In the second step, all *SNDVI* TS were decomposed into trend and sea-
 516 sonal components using the selected parameters (MRA-DWT, MRA-MODWT,
 517 best level (5) and MW). The choice of the optimal MW was based on the
 518 RMSE, D_{min} and r , as described, in section 4.1.

519 Fig.6 illustrates the RMSE derived from the trend component using the

Figure 6: RMSE boxplots derived from the trend component for all simulated TS and MW using both MRA-DWT (top) and MRA-MODWT (bottom).

to MRA-MODWT. *SNDVI2* and *SNDVI5* exhibited the highest RMSE as compared to *SNDVI1* and *SNDVI8* using the MRA-DWT. Similar results were obtained when using the seasonal components for all *SNDVI* and MRA-DWT. However, the RMSE differences were very small for MRA-MODWT. This is probably due to its redundancy property. In fact, MODWT wavelet redundancy facilitated the alignment between the decomposed wavelet and

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530 scaling coefficient at each level, thus enabling a ready comparison between
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11 the series and its decomposition (Paul and Birtchal, 2016). The feature of
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13 wavelet coefficients in MRA-MODWT lined up with the original TS in a
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15 meaningful way, resulting in low RMSE values for each MW.
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17 Fig.7 shows the RMSE boxplot for the different MW families. Using
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19 MRA-DWT, the Symlet MW family exhibited the lowest RMSE values (mean
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21 $RMSE \leq 0.018$) and narrowest ranges, followed by the daubechies family
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23 for all the simulated TS. This may be explained by the energy conservative
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25 properties of both MWs families. On the contrary, the biorthogonal and
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27 reverse biorthogonal families showed the highest variation (mean $RMSE \geq$
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29 0.025). In some cases, the RMSE values for biorthogonal wavelets is up
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31 to double the error derived for symlet wavelets (e.g. SNDVI1, SNDVI2,
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33 SNDVI5-7), probably due to the non-conservation energy of these MWs,
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35 which directly affects the decomposition. The same results were obtained for
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37 seasonal components analysis and different SNDVI using MRA-DWT and
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39 MRA-MODWT decomposition.
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41 Fig.8 shows the optimal MW (lowest RMSE and D_{min} and highest r) for
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43 each SNDVI. It was observed as the symlet family conveyed the best MW,
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45 with RMSE values that accounted for more than half of the RMSE obtained
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47 with the MRA-MODWT approach. The same results were obtained for all
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49 the simulated TS. Indeed, the symlet family was considered as the best MW
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51 for 92% and 64% of simulated TS based on trend and seasonal analysis,
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53 respectively. We can derive from this analysis that the MRA-DWT is the
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55 best WT type, which correspond to 99% and 72% of simulated TS for trend
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57 and seasonal analysis respectively.
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Figure 7: Boxplot for the RMSE derived from the trend components of the selected SNDVI TS using MRA-DWT. The different MW families (i.e., Daubechies (*db*), Coiflet (*Coif*), Symlet (*sym*), Meyer (*dmey*) biorthogonal (*bior*) and reverse biorthogonal (*rbio*)) are considered .

As a first conclusion based on simulated data, we have proved that MRA-DWT and level 5 could be considered as the best WT parameters. These findings are in accordance with the literature (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Rhif et al., 2021). Additionally, symlet and daubechies families are considered to be implemented with real data since they provided the best performance followed. Otherwise, the MWs with worst results (i.e., coiflet and reverse biorthogonal) are also considered.

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Figure 8: Optimal MW selection based on-trend and seasonal components using RMSE, D_{Mink} and r .

562 5.2. EO-based NDVI data

563 5.2.1. Best mother wavelet selection

564 The EO-based NDVI data were decomposed until level 5 according to the
 565 simulated results. Five MW families were considered to focus more deeply on
 566 the impact of the MW selection for vegetation change analysis. Particularly,
 567 two symlet MWs ($sym12$, $sym21$), daubechies MWs ($db14$), $dmey$, coiflet
 568 ($coif1$) and reverse biorthogonal ($rbio1.5$) are chosen. Symlet provided the
 569 best performance followed by daubechies and meyer, whereas coiflet and
 570 reverse biorthogonal exhibited the worst results.

571 In the first step, the Q_{NDVI} was calculated for the five MWs for the whole
 572 study area. Results showed as $sym21$, $sym12$, $db14$ and $dmey$ provided the

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10 573 same percentages of pixels for non-significant, positive and negative Q_{NDVI} ,
11 574 whereas, *rbio1.5* gave very different values. In general, all the MWs pro-
12
13 575 vided around 12% of the total pixels as non-significant as opposed to *rbio1.5*
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15 576 wavelet (19%) and *coif1* (14%). Positive and negative slopes were observed
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17 577 in 73% and 15% of the Q_{NDVI} values, respectively. Again, *rbio1.5* provided a
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19 578 different behaviour with 65% and 16% of positive and negative slopes values,
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21 579 respectively. The comparison between the different Theil-Sens slopes was
22
23 580 addressed for different land cover types. The RMSD and MBD were com-
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25 581 puted. Overall, the largest similarities were observed between *sym12* and
26
27 582 *db14* with the lowest difference error (RMSD=0.0659) for shrubland (SHR),
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29 583 grassland (GRS) and croplands (CROP) land cover. The highest dissimilar-
30
31 584 ity was given between *sym21* and *coif1* (RMSD=0.2569), greater than three
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33 585 times the lowest difference. Table 3 summarizes the correspondences for
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35 586 different land cover types. Slight differences were observed between *dmey-*
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37 587 *sym12* and *sym12-sym21* for different land cover types. Whereas *sym12*
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39 588 and *dmey* exhibited the lowest RMSD for forest (FS), savanna (SAV) and
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41 589 mosaics (MOS) land cover types, which may be explained by the similar
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43 590 properties (i.e. regularity, orthogonality, symmetry) between these MWs
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45 591 families. The highest discrepancies were observed when considering the pairs
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47 592 (*coif1-rbio 1.5*) and (*sym12-rbio 1.5*) for all the land cover types, which were
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49 593 in accordance with findings in section 5.1. Differences up to five times the
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51 594 lowest values were observed in forest (RMSD(*sym12-rbio1.5*) =0.0053) and
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53 595 mosaic (RMSD(*sym12-rbio1.5*) =0.0051) covers. These results are in agree-
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55 596 ment with those obtained using simulated data, where *rbio 1.5* and *coif1*
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57 597 presented the largest RMSE when using the trend component (section 5.1).

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Table 3: Root mean square differences (RMSD) and mean bias differences (MBD) resulted from the assessment performed between the different MW in the Mediterranean areas. MBD and RMSD are calculated considering different land cover types.

MWs	Statistic	FS	SHR	SAV	GRS	CROP	MOS
<i>sym21-</i>	RMSD	0.0011	0.0044	0.0015	0.0113	0.0033	0.0013
<i>sym12</i>	MBD	- 0.0004	0.0011	0	0.0002	0	-0.0002
<i>sym21-</i>	RMSD	0.0012	0.0060	0.0016	0.0477	0.0045	0.0014
<i>dmey</i>	MBD	-0.0003	-0.0001	-0.0001	-0.0004	-0.0001	0
<i>sym21-</i>	RMSD	0.0014	0.0044	0.0026	0.0355	0.0046	0.0015
<i>db14</i>	MBD	0.0005	0.0001	0.0003	-0.0001	0.0001	0.0003
<i>sym21-</i>	RMSD	0.0023	0.0216	0.0037	0.0271	0.0080	0.0028
<i>coif1</i>	MBD	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002	-0.0005	-0.0012	-0.0004
<i>sym21-</i>	RMSD	0.0049	0.0097	0.0056	0.1214	0.0168	0.0048
<i>rbio1.5</i>	MBD	0.0030	-0.0016	0.0013	0.0010	0.0020	0.0021
<i>sym12-</i>	RMSD	0.0009	0.0045	0.0014	0.0384	0.0045	0.0012
<i>dmey</i>	MBD	0.0001	-0.0012	0	-0.0006	-0.0001	0.0002
<i>sym12-</i>	RMSD	0.0017	0.0054	0.0030	0.0270	0.0045	0.0015
<i>db14</i>	MBD	0.0009	-0.0010	0.0003	-0.0003	0.0001	0.0004
<i>sym12-</i>	RMSD	0.0025	0.0211	0.0042	0.0268	0.0086	0.0029
<i>coif1</i>	MBD	0.0006	-0.0009	0.0002	-0.0007	-0.0012	-0.0003
<i>sym12-</i>	RMSD	0.0053	0.0106	0.0060	0.1394	0.0167	0.0051
<i>rbio1.5</i>	MBD	0.0033	-0.0026	0.0013	0.0007	0.0020	0.0022
<i>dmey-</i>	RMSD	0.0018	0.0075	0.0029	0.0250	0.0040	0.0016
<i>db14</i>	MBD	0.0008	0.0002	0.0003	0.0004	0.0002	0.0003

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Table 3: *Cont.*

MWs	Statistic	FS	SHR	SAV	GRS	CROP	MOS
<i>dmey-coif1</i>	RMSD	0.0025	0.0210	0.0039	0.0490	0.0094	0.0029
	MBD	0.0005	0.0004	0.0003	-0.0001	-0.0011	-0.0004
<i>dmey-rbio1.5</i>	RMSD	0.0052	0.0109	0.0057	0.1170	0.0144	0.0048
	MBD	0.0032	-0.0015	0.0013	0.0013	0.0021	0.0020
<i>Db14-coif1</i>	RMSD	0.0022	0.0234	0.0032	0.0406	0.0092	0.0027
	MBD	-0.0002	0.0001	0	-0.0005	-0.0013	-0.0007
<i>Db14-rbio1.5</i>	RMSD	0.0044	0.0094	0.0043	0.1181	0.0136	0.0044
	MBD	0.0025	-0.0016	0.0010	0.0009	0.0019	0.0018
<i>Coif1-rbio1.5</i>	RMSD	0.0047	0.0219	0.0054	0.1458	0.0204	0.0050
	MBD	0.0026	-0.0017	0.0010	0.0014	0.0031	0.0023

598 These differences were probably attributed to the different wavelet shapes
599 (i.e. *rbio 1.5* shows a rectangular shape, whereas a triangular shape is pre-
600 sented by *coif1*). In fact, the Coiflet wavelet showed a higher performance for
601 TS de-noising filter which is not the purpose of the long-term trends analysis
602 since a smoother component of the original TS is used (Dixit and Majumdar,
603 2013).

604 To gain an improve understanding on the best MW selection for trend
605 components, differences and similarities between *sym21*, *sym12*, *dmey* and
606 *db14* were fully analysed based on anomaly terms (z -score computation).
607 Mean slope and standard deviation (SDV) derived for the four MWs are

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10 608 shown in Fig.9. In general, clear evidence of positive NDVI trends dominate
11 609 over the study area with only a very few negative spot areas located in south-
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13 610 eastern Spain, northern Africa and south of Turkey, specifically in the cost
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15 611 of Adana, as opposed to the higher NDVI values observed in the central part
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17 612 of Turkey. The observed NDVI diminution in Tunisia mainly occurred in
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19 613 forest areas where degradation or forest fire events took place (Achour et al.,
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21 614 2018; Hasnaoui and Krott, 2019; Rhif et al., 2021). Spot areas with negative
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23 615 slopes were localized in eastern and south-eastern Spain belonging mainly to
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25 616 shrubland cover types (Fig. 3).

26
27 Fig.9 shows the z -score for the four MWs. The four z -score trend im-
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29 617 ages exhibit marked discrepancies. In general, grey colours (z -score around
30
31 618 zero) refer that the slope given by a particular wavelet is close to the mean
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33 619 of all the slopes whereas blue and red colours mean slope values larger and
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35 620 smaller than the mean, respectively. Differences up to 2 SDV were observed
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37 621 in the slope derived from different MWs. Particularly, *sym12* exhibited slope
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39 622 values lower than the mean slope with a total percentage of 16.51% pixels,
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41 623 mainly located in the Iberian Peninsula, North Africa, Sardinia and Sicily
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43 624 islands. This wavelet provided the lowest percentage of pixels with slope
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45 625 values below and above the mean (16.51% and 18.03%, respectively) and the
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47 626 highest number of identical pixels to the mean (z -score around 0). The values
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49 627 are deviated from the mean more than 1 SDV. By contrast, the *db14* pro-
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51 628 vided slope values larger than the mean in the Iberian Peninsula and Maroc
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53 629 (20.30%) but smaller slope values in central Europe and west Mediterranean
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55 630 countries. It provided the most different z -score compared to the mean and
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57 631 the highest negative z -score (30.26%) specifically in Italy with more than
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633 1.5 SDV, Romania and Ukraine. *sym21* and *dmey* wavelets showed similar
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11 634 slopes except for Turkey. *Dmey* exhibited the highest percentage of pixels
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13 with slopes larger than the mean (24.12%), specifically in Turkey.
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Figure 9: Standard deviation (a), mean slope (b) for all MW and Z-score values from the different Sens slope (Q) using four MWs: *sym21*(c), *sym12*(d), *dmey* (e) and *db14*(f).

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636 The trend derived from *sym12*, *db14*, *dmey* and *sym21* show significantly
637 differences between them. The selection of a particular wavelet for each pixel

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 638 may be a solution to improve precision. To account for this advantage, the
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 11 energy to Shannon entropy ratio was enriched from the knowledge gained
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 13 using simulated scenarios in the sense that only a selection of MWs demon-
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 15 strated to become a proper choice for vegetation change analysis. This study
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 17 provided insights into the capabilities of different MWs for trend analysis
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 19 using EO-based NDVI TS at pixel level and at inter-annual temporal scale.
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 21 Moreover, the selection of only a few MWs makes the computation of Shan-
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 23 non entropy reliable and practical in terms of computational cost meaning at
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 25 regional scale. The results (Fig.10) lead to a widespread distribution of the
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Figure 10: Best MW pixel-wise selection based on energy to Shannon entropy ratio.

646
 647 three MWs, revealing the *sym12* as the most dominated wavelet (40.42%),
 648 followed by *db14* (26.48%) and *sym21* (25.54%). On the contrary, *dmey* pro-
 649 vided the lowest percentage of pixels (7.56%). *Sym12* wavelet is distinctly
 650 presented in forest land covers with more than 60% of the pixels (table 4).

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651 This may be explained by the presence of the largest wavelength in *sym12*,
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11 652 which can lead to improve the periodic change detection in deciduous forest.
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13 653 Similarly, *sym12* showed the highest percentage (around 51%) for savanna
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15 654 land cover, specifically in Bulgaria and Romania which faces an increase in
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17 655 SPI between 2001 and 2019. In fact, the savanna land cover has shown
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19 656 highly seasonal rainfall and prominent inter-annual climate variability, mak-
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21 657 ing them one of the most dynamic global biomes (Ma et al., 2013). The
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23 658 percentages are very similar between *db14*, *sym12* and *sym21* for grasslands,
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25 659 cropland and mosaic. Marked differences are more significant between re-
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27 660 gions than land covers. For example, *sym21* is dominated over cropland in
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29 661 north Africa, and Greece, whereas *sym12* was prevailed in eastern Spain.
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31 662 More precisely, *sym12* and *sym21* may have shown a proper alternative for
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33 663 grassland and cropland. This may be explained by the similar number of
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35 664 oscillations between *sym12* and *sym21*, which can help in the detection of
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37 665 a periodic change in croplands. The short-wavelength of *sym21* may lead
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39 666 to suit better for cropland land cover. In addition, both land cover types
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41 667 showed a marked seasonal pattern highly influenced by precipitation. *Db14*
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43 668 was dominated in shrubland, probably due to the fact that *db14* provides
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45 669 with the greatest number of oscillations with a different amplitude, being
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47 670 more sensitive to small variations in shrubland dynamics. As was expected,
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49 671 *dmey* exhibits the lowest percentage for all land covers with more presence
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51 672 in the west part of Spain, central part of France and northern areas of Italy.
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53 673 These findings prove that *dmey* seems not to be the most appropriate MW
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55 674 in remote sensing applications despite it is frequently used in the literature.

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675 Fig.11 illustrates the slope derived when considering the best MW (Fig.11a)

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Table 4: Best MW selection using land cover type.

	<i>Db14</i>	<i>Dmey</i>	<i>sym12</i>	<i>sym21</i>
Forest	19.64%	3.12%	60.90%	16.34%
Shrubland	33.59%	10.29%	24.58%	31.54%
Savanna	24.35%	8.38%	50.98%	16.29%
Grassland	28.64%	5.64%	36.28%	29.44%
Cropland	27.82%	8.12%	32.92%	31.14%
Mosaic	24.64%	14.57%	38.40%	22.39%

676 along with its associated relative error (RE) (Fig.11b). The Q_{NDVI} clearly
677 indicates a tendency to positive trends with very limited negative areas.
678 Quantifying and understanding the uncertainty associated to inter-annual
679 vegetation changes strongly depends on the error introduced by the best
680 MW selection and the Theil-Sens slope method. In this case, a small RE
681 (i.e. $-20\% < RE < 20\%$) is observed in 59.80% of the Mediterranean area.
682 However, almost identical percentages were obtained when the trend image
683 was derived using the *sym12* (Fig.11d). Slightly lower values (58.65%) are
684 shown by the *db14* (Fig.11f). The Q_{NDVI} for *sym12* (Fig.11c) and *db14*
685 (Fig.11e) indicate also a clear tendency to positive trends with very limited
686 negative areas. Circa 47% of pixels with slope around zero are observed for
687 the three methods (in grey) with 12% of non-significant pixels (in black) ob-
688 served for the three trend images. The Q_{NDVI} derived using the best MW,
689 *sym12* and *db14* exhibit very few differences. Only 5.2%, 5.3% and 5.4%
690 of pixels belong to negative trend values for best MW, *sym12* and *db14*,

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Figure 11: The Q_{NDVI} along with its relative error for best MW, *sym12* and *db14*.

691 respectively. Similar results are obtained with positive slope.

692 These results suggest that the error due to the Theil-Sens slope method
 693 become an important tool to assess the uncertainty associated to the trend
 694 estimation (lower than 15%), with the lowest values given for bare soil, crop-
 695 land and shrubland areas (table 5), respectively. The similar RE images
 696 derived for the best MW (i.e., pixel-wise selection based on energy to Shan-

697 non entropy ratio), *sym12* and *db14* lead to consider the error due to best
 698 MW (between the *sym12*, *sym21*, *db14* and *dmey*) as negligible as compared
 699 to the Theil-Sens slope method. These findings are in concordance with the
 700 RMSD differences provided in Table 3, where mean absolute differences up to
 701 0.2091 (20.91% in relative terms for a mean trend value of 0.1) are observed
 for all the possible comparisons between the four considered wavelets.

Table 5: Relative mean error (%) by land cover type for best MW, *sym12* and *db14*.

	Best MW	<i>sym12</i>	<i>Db14</i>
Forest	13.9%	13.9%	14.4%
Shrubland	10.2%	9.6%	10.2%
Savanna	12.5%	12.4%	12.9%
Grassland	11.4%	10.9%	11.7%
Cropland	8.9%	8.7%	8.8%
Mosaic	12.3%	12.5%	12.5%

702
 703 **Two main conclusions are derived regarding the MW choice. On the one**
 704 **hand, the best MW obtained with energy entropy ratio has proven a useful**
 705 **approach to generate a more accurate trend image and to benchmark differ-**
 706 **ent MWs over the Mediterranean area. This choice considers the vegetation**
 707 **change depending on the country and land cover type. This method gives**
 708 **a very high precision, but can be more computationally consuming. The**
 709 **succeed in the Shannon entropy computation may depend on the MW selec-**
 710 **tion considered as input. This study has taken benefit from the simulation**
 711 **exercise, gaining a better understanding of the different vegetation TS be-**

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10 712 haviour. On the other hand, as an alternative to the best MW that may
11 713 offer a more practical application, we propose the *sym12* as a potential MW
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13 714 for inter-annual vegetation trend analysis in the Mediterranean area. *Sym12*
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15 715 have shown a very small RE (lower than 15%) in the vegetation trend es-
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17 716 timation for most of the 55% of the study area on the same order that the
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19 717 error introduced when different wavelets are derived for the same pixel.

21 718 5.2.2. Evaluation of the proposed method

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24 719 In this section, we evaluate the obtained results against three datasets
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26 720 in other areas with different spatial and temporal resolutions as described in
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28 721 section 3.2.5.

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30 722 Fig.12 shows a comparative study between Q_{NDVI} using MODIS 16-day
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32 723 1km, MODIS 16-day 500m, MODIS 16-day 250m and MODIS monthly 1km,
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34 724 in eastern Spain and north of Tunisia. In eastern Spain, no significant differ-
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36 725 ences were observed when the spatial resolution is changed as it can observed
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38 726 from MODIS 16-day 1km, MODIS 16-day 500m and MODIS 16-day 250m.
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40 727 The percentage of non-significant (9.15%, 8.23% and 8.65%) and negative
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42 728 (14.80%, 13.87% and 15.83%) slopes was almost the same. More impor-
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44 729 tant differences are observed for positive values with 33.22%, 40.59% and
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46 730 40.70% using MODIS 16-day 1km, MODIS 16-day 500m and MODIS 16-day
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48 731 250m, respectively, which belongs mainly to croplands, grasslands and mixed
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50 732 forest with mixed vegetation characteristics (Costa-Saura et al., 2021). How-
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52 733 ever, a remarkable difference is observed regarding the percentage of negative
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54 734 (14.80% and 19.32%) and positive (33.22% and 55.12%) when the temporal
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56 735 resolution is considered from the analysis of MODIS 16-day 1km and MODIS
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58 736 monthly 1 km, respectively. The Q_{NDVI} obtained using MODIS monthly 1km

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Figure 12: The Q_{NDVI} in the east of Spain (Top) and north-west of Tunisia (down) using different datasets (i.e., MODIS 16-day 1km, MODIS Monthly 1km, MODIS 16-day 250m and MODIS 16-day 500m) for *sym12* MW.

737 have an important number of pixels of positive data which doesn't agree with
738 the literature (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Costa-Saura et al., 2021).

739 In north of Tunisia, a slight difference is presented in non-significant
740 (15.71%, 12.56% and 11.42%) values when the spatial resolution is anal-
741 ysed. Markedly dissimilarities are obtained for negative (20%, 16.34% and

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742 15.78%) and positive (29.11%, 40.76% and 46.41%) values for MODIS 16-day
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11 743 1km, 500m and 250m, respectively. The differences may be attributed to the
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13 744 mixed vegetation type observed in the north of Tunisia (Rhif et al., 2021).
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15 745 However, very high non-significant (26.1%) and negative (33.68%) values are
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17 746 obtained when the temporal resolution is monthly.

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19 747 Based on the obtained results we can conclude that the obtained WT pa-
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21 748 rameters (level 5, *sym12* and MRA-DWT) could be generalised for different
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23 749 spatial resolutions. However, the temporal resolution affects the results and
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25 750 more significant pixels are obtained when the temporal resolution is higher.
26
27 751 This is due probably to the level of decomposition which is calculated based
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29 752 on timescale (eq.3, eq.4). This is in accordance with the findings risen from
30
31 753 the comparison of two studies focused on Spain, where daily and annual data
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33 754 set are used as inputs in the analysis of long-term vegetation changes using
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35 755 the MRA-WT (Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2019; Martínez et al., 2022).

36 37 756 5.2.3. *Vegetation change analysis*

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39 757 The vegetation dynamic analysis in the Mediterranean area using the
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41 758 best selected WT parameters (i.e. MRA-DWT, level 5 and *sym12* MW) is
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43 759 complemented using the mean NDVI behaviour at inter-annual scale (\bar{A}_5),
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45 760 seasonal behaviour by means of the time of maximum development (NDVI
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47 761 t_{max}) and correlation with precipitation.

48
49 762 The (\bar{A}_5) provides the vegetation status at inter-annual scale (Fig.13a).
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51 763 74.32% of pixels show high NDVI mean values (i.e. NDVI mean > 0.4), mainly
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53 764 localized in Europe (except the south of Spain), Tunisia and Algeria. These
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55 765 results agree with previous studies (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009; Rhif et al.,
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57 766 2021; Senf and Seidl, 2021). Similarly, the natural vegetation mosaic and

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Figure 13: NDVI mean from \bar{A}_5 (a) and t_{max} (b) derived from MRA-DWT using *sym12* for vegetation change analysis in the Mediterranean area between 2001-2019.

767 savanna in Europe showed a high NDVI mean. However, low NDVI mean
768 values (i.e. NDVI mean<0.4) are observed near coastline regions (i.e. north
769 of Africa, south Spain and middle east). It is presented principally in crop-

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770 land and grassland where a high variability was expected in the vegetation
771 dynamics.

772 The NDVI t_{max} is calculated from the D_4 component (Fig.13b). Most pix-
773 els in Europe (except the south of Spain) and Turkey show values between
774 June, July and August characteristics of summer-peaking vegetation (such
775 as forests in northern Spain and Europe, see Fig.3) and some paddy irrigated
776 land covers. However, the majority of pixels around the Mediterranean Sea
777 (i.e. north of Africa, south Spain and middle east) exhibit a t_{max} in February
778 (blue). In all North Africa countries, these pixels mainly correspond to shur-
779 blands, savanna, grasslands and sparse crops (Schilling et al., 2020), which
780 have a remarkable change in their canopies during the years. In fact, it is
781 covered by herbaceous cover in winter that it is removed by tilling in the
782 summer. This agricultural method leads to higher NDVI rating in February
783 (Gilabert et al., 1994). In Fig.13b, the light blue areas along the Mediter-
784 ranean coastline are citrus orchards (Martínez and Gilabert, 2009). Pixels
785 with green colour (e.g. Italy and north Algeria) belong to spring-peaking
786 vegetation (i.e. t_{max} in April) where precipitation is the main controlling
787 factor.

788 To further study the results as a function of precipitation, the relationship
789 between Q_{NDVI} and SPI trend (Q_{SPI}) using best MW (i.e. *sym12*) is ex-
790 ploited to analyse the land cover change and the impact of climatic data in the
791 Mediterranean area. The Q_{SPI} over the studied period was computed based
792 on a multiple linear regression procedure to locate areas affected by drought
793 or wet events (Fig.14a). Areas with rainfall excess or deficit are shown in
794 green and red colors, respectively. The trend analysis and correlation with

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Figure 14: a) Trend of the SPI index computed from 2001 to 2019. b) correlation between Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI} . Green colour relates positive Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI} (#1), blue colour corresponds to negative Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI} (#2), red colour show pixels with negative Q_{NDVI} and positive Q_{SPI} (#3), and dark green colour show pixels with positive Q_{NDVI} and negative Q_{SPI} (#4.)

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10 795 vegetation was calculated shifting SPI series two months compressing the pe-
11 796 riod of maximum vegetation development. Fig.14b shows that around 32%
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13 797 of pixels show a high agreement between Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI} . In fact, 21.97%
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15 798 and 3.52% correspond to positive Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI} and negative Q_{NDVI}
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17 799 and Q_{SPI} , respectively. However, 1.78% have negative Q_{NDVI} and positive
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19 800 Q_{SPI} , and 14.19% have positive Q_{NDVI} and negative Q_{SPI} , respectively. As
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21 801 a conclusion, a positive Q_{NDVI} change was observed in the majority of the
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23 802 Mediterranean area (Fig.11). More specifically, a high value was presented in
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25 803 Turkey, Greece and North Africa. This is probably due to the high agreement
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27 804 with precipitation (positive Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI}). Regarding the selection of
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29 805 areas affected by long-term land degradation processes, a major presence was
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31 806 located in the middle east of Tunisia, Algeria and Spain. This change may
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33 807 be attributed to the diminution of precipitation (negative Q_{NDVI} and Q_{SPI})
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35 808 in the studied period. Algeria and Tunisia have similarly shaped plot areas.
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37 809 In both countries, the importance of rain for agriculture is a key weakness,
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39 810 while a relatively high income level strengthens the adaptive capacity. Egypt
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41 811 has the highest generic adaptive capacity and lowest sensitivity to climate
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43 812 change. However, the land degradation observed in Iraq and Syria did not
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45 813 show correlation with climatic change (negative Q_{NDVI} and positive Q_{SPI})
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47 814 This degradation is probably due to the land cover change in this area as
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49 815 presented in Fig.3. These results agree with the work of Allawai and Ahmed
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51 816 (2020) where they proved that there was a negative trend in this area due to
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53 817 the decrease in surface area of the water body represented by Mosul Lake.
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818 **6. Conclusion**

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819 The spatio-temporal analysis based on non-stationary NDVI MODIS TS
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13 is heavily sensitive to the used methodology. Therefore, different methods
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15 can lead to opposite results. For this reason, it is quite straightforward to
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17 run a sensitivity analysis that takes into consideration all parameters, as was
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19 done in this study.
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824 The obtained results are presented **as follow**:

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825 1. Simulating TS with varying trend, seasonality and noise revealed that
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26 MRA-DWT is more robust than MRA-MODWT for vegetation change
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28 analysis. In fact, 99% and 72% of simulated TS have proved the ef-
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30 fectiveness of MRA-DWT for trend and seasonal analysis respectively.
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32 Additionally, the symlet family was considered as the best MW for 92%
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34 and 64% of simulated TS based on-trend and seasonal analysis, respec-
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36 tively. Also, the level 5 is obtained as the best level of decomposition.
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832 2. The obtained results with simulation analysis are then translated to
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39 a real case. Therefore, the best level of decomposition and best type
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41 (i.e. MRA-DWT) were applied to decompose the NDVI TS extracted
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43 from MODIS images (2001-2019) for the Mediterranean area. This step
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45 focused deeply to select the best MW depending to the NDVI TS char-
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47 acteristics. As opposed to other contributions, our work considers the
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49 more general question of understanding the effectiveness of different
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51 wavelets families and optimizing the selection of the most appropriate
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53 MW in EO-based data analysis for different land cover types. As main
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55 findings, *sym12* was more dominated in all area with 36.12% specifi-
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842 cally for forest, savanna and mosaic land cover, followed by *db14* with

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9 843 29.17% and *sym21* with 36.21%. *sym21* and *db14* were dominated in
10 844 cropland.

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13 845 3. For the selection of the best MW, the energy to entropy ratio gives the
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15 846 most precise MW for each pixel. This choice considers the vegetation
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17 847 change depending to the country and land cover type. Additionally, we
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19 848 propose that *sym12* could be considered as the best MW for vegetation
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21 849 analysis in the Mediterranean area.

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23 850 Overall, there were two obvious advantages to the proposed methodology.
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25 851 First, the MRA-WT was able to analyse vegetation changes by decomposing
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27 852 the non-stationary NDVI TS. Second, the proposed methodology selects the
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29 853 optimal WT parameters to improve the trend and seasonal change analysis.
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31 854 **Additionally, the proposed method could be generalized using different spa-**
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33 855 **tial resolution.** In consideration of the good general performance of this
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35 856 new methodology, future activities will consider, in a first step, to extend
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37 857 the results using different remotely sensed TS (AVHRR, Landsat, sentinel 2,
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39 858 MODIS). In fact, more details could be detected with low spatial resolution.
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41 859 Whereas, the computational time of execution is considered as major prob-
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43 860 lem. Additionally, this methodology can be extended to predict vegetation
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45 861 change in Mediterranean area. Thus, a hybrid methodology based on best
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47 862 WT parameters and deep learning model could be considered.

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50 863 **Credit author statement**

51
52 864 Manel Rhif: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis,
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54 865 Funding acquisition, Investigation, Visualization, Writing - original draft,
55
56 866 Writing - review and editing. Ali ben Abbes: Conceptualization, Methodol-

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867 ogy, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Supervision, Writing - re-
868 view and editing. Beatriz Martínez: Conceptualization, Methodology, Soft-
869 ware, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Supervision, Writing -
870 review and editing. Imed Riadh Farah: Methodology, Visualization, Writ-
871 ing - review and editing. María Amparo Gilabert: Methodology, Resource,
872 Writing and editing- review.

873 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

874 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial inter-
875 ests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work
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1151 **Acronyms**

- 1152 A: Approximation component
1153 bior*M.N*: BiorSpline

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- 1154 Coif N : Coiflet
- 1155 CWT: Continuous wavelet transforms
- 1156 D: Detail component
- 1157 db N : Daubechies
- 1158 D_{mink} : Minkowski distance
- 1159 DWT: Discrete wavelet transforms
- 1160 EO:Earth observation
- 1161 HP: High pass filter
- 1162 LP: Low pass filter
- 1163 MBD: Mean bias difference
- 1164 MODIS: Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiomete
- 1165 MODWT: Maximal Overlap Discrete Wavelet Transform
- 1166 MRA: Multi resolution analysis
- 1167 MW: Mother wavelet
- 1168 NDVI: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
- 1169 Q : Theil-Sen's Slope
- 1170 r : Pearson correlation
- 1171 rbio $M.N$: ReverseBior
- 1172 RE: Relative error
- 1173 RMSD: Root mean square Difference
- 1174 RMSE: Root mean square error
- 1175 R(S): Energy to entropy Ratio
- 1176 SDG: Sustainable development goals
- 1177 SDV: Standard deviation
- 1178 SNDVI: simulated NDVI data

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9	1179 SPI: standardized Precipitation Index
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11	1180 sSNDVI: seasonal simulated NDVI data
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13	1181 sym N : Symlet
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15	1182 t_{max} : timing of maximum NDVI
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17	1183 TS: Time series
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19	1184 tSNDVI: trend simulated NDVI data
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21	1185 WT: Wavelet transform
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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: